

DYNAMIC GEOMETRY AS AN INTEGRAL COMPONENT OF ELITE MATHEMATICS TEACHERS TRAINING

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The most of modern research is aimed at studying the elite as a political or economic phenomenon (political elite, business elite e. g.). The concept of «pedagogical elite» has not yet acquired a stable definition, and it is not included in the latest pedagogical, psychological, and sociological encyclopedias and dictionaries. There are single publications devoted to this topic but attempts to formulate a definition of the pedagogical elite, unfortunately, come down to political science formulations and general words. It all comes down to spiritual and moral values. No one objects to this thesis, but if we are talking about the professional training of a teacher, he must master certain competencies that will make him truly a representative of an elite group. And here you can't answer with general phrases about information technology [1, 2].

It seems to us that at this stage it is more correct to speak not about the formation of the teaching elite in general, but to consider some (albeit limited at this stage) specific approaches to the formation of the teaching elite, in this case, the elite of mathematics teachers.

Representatives of such an elite group should not only occupy some position in society but also “benefit” from this. It is put in quotation marks because the benefit is understood not just as some kind of personal benefit, but as a benefit for their business, for the level of teaching mathematics in this case.

Such teachers should be ready to give lectures (or their fragments) of a new type, which form the foundations of mathematical discourse for students. Therefore, during their studies, they must attend such lectures. A novelty in the formation of educational mathematical discourse is cognitive visualization (especially of

mathematical objects, the representation of which and operation with which is difficult). Yet Albert Einstein noted, “If I can’t picture it, I can’t understand it.”

Visual analytics makes it possible to use the enormous potentialities of a person’s spatial and imaginative reasoning and finds application in many areas of activity: scientific research, design work, information security, financial monitoring and so on.

Hamming’s famous aphorism “The purpose of computing is insight, not numbers” can certainly be applied not only to scientific research but also to teaching mathematics, since any training (learning) contains elements of scientific research. As a result, the scientific direction «Scientific visualization», which develops methods and tools for understanding the problems being solved by involving the ability of a person to see and understand images in data analysis, is very relevant for the pedagogical mathematical community [3].

It should be noted that scientific visualization is not only a computer tool. It is also a methodology for working with it. Otherwise, we will get just computer cartoons.

About a hundred years ago, American researchers discovered that the stereoscopic representation during learning enhances spatial imagination and understanding of three-dimensional objects and scenes. This representation can stimulate the manifestation of intuition (insight) in schoolchildren and students, which serves as the basis for “guessing” when solving problems and which rarely occurs with traditional teaching methods. Visual immersion is achieved by creating a stereo effect of the observed artificial scene. These possibilities can also be briefly characterized with the metaphor of “seeing the invisible”, which is very relevant for mathematical objects that are ideal by their nature, and we do observe and display their models.

Unfortunately, the emergence of appropriate computer tools (dynamic geometry programs – GeoGebra, for example) has gone almost unnoticed by modern mathematics methodological literature. As a result, the solving of stereometric problems (both problems requiring an illustrative drawing and construction ones)

continues in traditional ways in a projection drawing. This approach has a big concomitant problem – the lack of feedback. Seymour Papert just wrote about the importance of such a connection. If there is no feedback (or it is weak), then the teacher cannot effectively control the process of obtaining knowledge by the student. This happens because he does not see the real reason for the student's error – these are incorrect actions to solve the problem or an incorrect projection drawing of the correct solution. At the same time, self-control cannot be learned either, because the student himself does not see *how*, *where*, and *why* he made a mistake. That is, the very fact of an error exists, but the student may not even notice it, not realize it, but consider that he solved the problem correctly. As a consequence, there is always a certain amount of erroneous works completed and submitted in the belief that they are correct. Therefore, objective control is needed – additional “eyes” are needed.

It is known that the rotation of objects concerning in the field of view of the observer forms a three-dimensional perception of space. Note that we do not see the object itself, but its projection on the screen, on film, etc. That is we observe a successive change of projections of a three-dimensional object. So, in contrast to the usual static parallax, which causes a normal binocular stereo effect, here we have a motion parallax. At relatively low speeds of rotation of the object, such a parallax displacement leads to the formation of a corresponding spatial image.

Thus, in addition to the possibility of working in space (albeit perceived in subjective reality), feedback is added. This allows the student to control the results of his work. In addition, the teacher also sees the real results of the student's work and does not try to guess from the projection drawing what the student did (or wanted to do). Errors (if any) are clearly visible in the three-dimensional drawing, and the teacher can give specific recommendations on how to eliminate them. This is especially effective in cases where the student has made a mistake but does not see it himself. Then the teacher has the opportunity not only to point out the error but also to analyze together with the student the cause of its occurrence and indicate ways to prevent it [4].

Visualization can be effectively used in the study of solid geometry by clearly demonstrating the features of theorems.

For example, let's take a pyramid with the lateral edges inclined to the base at the same angles. Then the top of the pyramid is projected into the center of the circle circumscribed around its base. The spatial demonstration (Fig. 1) shows what happens when the base is not only an equilateral triangle but also a triangle of a different kind. For example, here we have a triangle with an obtuse angle as the base of the pyramid that is why its apex is projected beyond the base.

*Spatial drawing
of the pyramid*

*Pyramid projection
on the plane of its base*

Fig. 1. Pyramid with lateral edges inclined to the base at the same angles

It is also possible to implement an unconventional approach to 3D construction problems, going beyond the projection drawing.

*Fig. 2. Solution of the problem of constructing a tetrahedron
with the base given and the angles between the base and lateral faces*

Let's consider another example. Construct a tetrahedron with the base given and the angles between the base and lateral faces (Fig. 2). This problem is a spatial analogue of the classical planimetric problem – “Construct a triangle given a side and two angles adjacent to it.” While solving this problem, there is a need to construct dihedral angles from their known linear ones [5].

It should also be noted that the images in the above figures can be rotated, thereby creating a dynamic stereo effect.

Thus, the use of scientific visualization tools allows you to raise the teaching of mathematics to a new cognitive level. And teachers who have mastered this method and use it in their professional work can certainly be attributed to the real pedagogical elite of our educational society.

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